

Evaluation of urea forms in thaladi rice (IR20)

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We compared the performance of 75 kg N/ha as urea supergranules (USG), sulfur-coated urea (SCU), lac-coated urea (LCU), and gypsum-coated urea (Gyp-U) to split application (50% N basal, 25% N at tillering, and 25% N at panicle initiation) of prilled urea (PU). USG was point-placed at the center of 4 hills 2 d after transplanting. SCU, LCU,

and Gyp-U were broadcast and incorporated before planting.

P and K (22 kg P/ha, 42 kg K/ha) were applied basally. Soil was clay loam, low in available N, medium to high in available P and K contents. The trial was conducted during 1985-86 thaladi (Sep-Feb) with IR20 seedlings transplanted at 20 × 19-cm spacing. Grain yield was computed at 14% moisture.

SCU yielded over 1.9 t/ha more than control and gave 70 kg grain/kg N. All other forms of urea yielded more than split application of urea (see table). ☞

Comparative yield with different forms of urea in 1985-86 thaladi. Aduthurai, India.

Urea form	Yield ^a (t/ha)	Yield increase (t/ha)	N efficiency (kg grain/kg N)
Control	3.36 b	—	—
PU	4.34 a	0.98	58
USG	4.84 a	1.48	65
SCU	5.26 a	1.90	70
LCU	4.44 a	1.08	59
Gyp-U	4.40 a	1.04	59

^aMeans followed by a common letter are not significantly different at 5% level by DMRT.

Response of Magsanaya upland rice in an acidic upland area to lime and fertilizer

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The effects on Magsanaya upland rice of lime and different kinds of fertilizer were studied in a split-plot design. Soil was an Ultisol, clay loam with pH 4.0, 4% organic matter, 6 ppm available P (Olsen), and 60 ppm H₂SO₄ extractable K.

Liming at 6 t/ha was assigned to the main plot. Different fertilizers were

Yield response of Magsanaya upland rice to lime and various fertilizers. Panay Island, Philippines.

Fertilizer	Yield ^a (t/ha)	
	No lime	6 t lime/ha
35-35-35 kg NPK/ha	2.20 b	2.30 a
28-28-28 kg NPK + 100 kg commercial organic fertilizer	2.08 b	2.02 b
28-28-28 kg NPK + 1.8 t bat cave rock phosphate mixed with bagasse ash	2.50 a	2.43 a
10 t dried chicken dung	1.17 c	1.39 c
20 t fresh azolla	0.54 d	.86 d
No fertilizer	0.43 d	.72 d
CV (%)	Main Plot —	12.81 (ns)
	Subplot —	6.3 (s.)

^aSeparation of means by Duncan's multiple range test at the 5% level.

assigned to the subplots (see table).

Lime, chicken dung, and azolla were broadcast and incorporated 1 mo before planting. Other fertilizers were applied just before planting.

Applying lime did not significantly increase yield. Chicken dung and azolla were not as good as commercial NPK, either alone or in mixture (see table). ☞

Rice-Based Cropping Systems

A suitable cropping system for Thambiraparanj region in Tamil Nadu

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In Thambiraparanj region of Tirunelveli District in Tamil Nadu, a two-crop system — a short-duration rice during first season (Jun-Sep) and a medium-duration rice during second season (Oct-Feb) — is generally followed. We conducted an experiment to find a suitable three-crop system, by raising a

third crop of pulses and oil seeds during summer depending on available soil moisture and summer showers. We tested five crops (Table 1).

Black gram, green gram, and soybean seeds were dibbled without land preparation and groundnut seeds were dibbled after land preparation. Spacing was 30 cm between rows for all, and 10 cm between plants for black gram and soybean and 15 cm for green gram and groundnut. Seed rate was 20 kg/ha for black gram and soybean, 37.5 kg/ha for green gram, and 100 kg/ha for groundnut. Gingelly seeds were broadcast after land preparation at

Table 1. Crops tested in the summer season, 1984-85, Paddy Experiment Station, Ambasamuduram, Tamil Nadu, India.

Crop	Variety	Duration (d)	Sowing date
Black gram (<i>Vigna mungo</i>)	Co. 5	76	17 Feb 1985
Green gram (<i>Vigna radiata</i>)	Co. 4	92	17 Feb 1985
Soybean (<i>Glycine max</i>)	Co. 1	94	17 Feb 1985
Groundnut (<i>Arachis hypogaea</i>)	Co. 2	112	19 Feb 1985
Gingelly (<i>Sesamum indicum</i>)	Co. 1	96	6 Mar 1985